

USING OF IMAGINATION IN DEVELOPING VOCABULARY

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Abstract: This article examines how important learning English is, the importance of vocabulary in language acquisition, the role of methods and imagination in increasing vocabulary as well as issues of using memorization and emotions.

Key words: Cubic, imagination, building, mechanism, association, cub

Introduction: In this era of constant development, knowing foreign languages is of great importance and is also key requirement for all young people. This is because if you want to master foreign expertise or delve deeper into the secrets of business and develop it on a global scale, one of the most essential factors is the extent which you know a foreign language.

Literature review: Imagination is a powerful tool for vocabulary building. This method, used alongside other memorization techniques, involves not just memorizing new words but also visualizing and feeling them as if they were native. This allows for smoother communication and quicker recall as the right associations come to mind more easily.

Methodology: This study is based on the importance of learning English and different ways of memorizing words with the use of imagination. Different productive methods in parallel with other memorization methods. The method helps to remember and interactivity helps to reinforce them at an unconscious level.

Results: The methods indicated that memory and emotions are very powerful mechanisms for influencing vocabulary, every small detail may not be remembered but it is difficult to forget exactly what experiences caused this or that event to be added into memory. The basis of this approach is that it is not enough to simply memorize each foreign word, but it is necessary to mentally animate it and connect it with equivalent in your native language. By following this approach, it is possible to think

and communicate freely in a foreign language and avoid wasting extra time in searching for the answer.

Discussion: When learning the word "cup" in English visualize a cup and repeat the word. To memorize a longer word like "big" first imagine a large, luxurious building and repeat the word. Another method is to create a sentence in your mind using the words you are trying to learn. This will help you remember related words during a conversation and prevent you from forgetting the target word.

Conclusion: This study emphasizes that beautiful speech is an ability that can be acquired through working on oneself. Any ability can be developed. For this you need to have a desire and work tirelessly every day. Your language richness depends only on your personal efforts. Because we are living in the 21st century, this acquires knowing all things related to English. English is a key for all information about the world.

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